

**The Framework Programme for Research & Innovation
Innovation actions (IA)**

Project Title:

A Novel Adaptive Cybersecurity Framework for the Internet-of-Vehicles

nloVe

Grant Agreement No: 833742

[H2020-SU-ICT-01-2018] Dynamic countering of cyber-attacks

Deliverable

D8.9 Detailed Dissemination and communication plan - v1

Deliverable No.		D8.9	
Workpackage No.	WP8	Workpackage and task type	Title Dissemination, Exploitation & Standardization
Task No.	T8.1	Task Title	Task 8.1 Communication & Dissemination Activities
Lead beneficiary		SEEMS	
Dissemination level		PU	
Nature of Deliverable		R	
Delivery date		30 October 2020	
Status		Final	
File Name:		WP Activities_WP8.1_Deliverables_D8.9 - Detailed Dissemination and Communication Plan_nloVe_report-v1.0	
Project start date, duration		01 May 2019, 36 Months	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement n°833742

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Document history			
Version	Date	Status	Modifications made by
0.1	20/10/2020	Chapter 8: sub-Chapters 8.2 and 8.3 replaced with sub-chapter 8.2 “Communication & Dissemination Activities Year 1(M1-M12)”, Chapter 9 “External communication and dissemination activities for Year 2 (M13-M24)” added, Updated Chapters 10 and 11 (Chapter 9 and 10 in v1.1)	SEEMS
0.2	23/10/2020	Review	KENOTOM
0.3	23/10/2020	Review	CERTH
1.0	30/10/2020	Final version for submission	SEEMS

List of definitions & abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
WP	Work Package
CAV	Connected & Autonomous Vehicle
ML	Machine Learning
IoV	Internet of Vehicles
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats
CSIRTs	Computer Security Incident Response Teams
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the second-revised version of the dissemination and communication plan for the nloVe project. It provides the overall project dissemination and communication strategy as well as the key stakeholders, communication channels and dissemination materials to be used. A detailed breakdown of the communication activities that take place during the first eighteen months of the project implementation is also presented. This deliverable will be updated in months 27 and 36 of the project's implementation. These updates will include the evaluation of the communication activities for the previous period with the aim of improving the project's dissemination strategy to achieve maximum impact of the project results.

Table of Contents

List of definitions & abbreviations.....	3
Executive Summary	4
List of Figures.....	7
List of Tables	8
1 Introduction.....	9
1.1 Purpose, Context and Scope of this Deliverable.....	9
1.2 Deliverable Structure.....	10
2 Dissemination and Communication strategy.....	11
2.1 Overall objectives.....	11
2.2 Strategy Approach.....	11
2.3 Roles in the consortium.....	12
3 Communication and dissemination principles.....	14
3.1 General Principles	14
3.2 EU Communication Rules.....	14
3.2.1 Obligation to disseminate results	14
3.2.2 Open access to scientific publications.....	15
3.2.3 Open access to research data.....	15
3.2.4 Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem.....	16
3.2.5 Disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility	16
3.2.6 Consequences of non-compliance	16
4 Stakeholder Communities	17
5 Tailored messages	20
5.1 General message.....	20
5.2 Extended general message.....	20
5.3 Scientific and educational message	20
5.4 Message for the general public	21
6 Communication channels	23
6.1 Website	23
6.2 Social networks	24
6.3 (Joint-) events.....	27
6.4 Newsletters	27
6.5 Resources available via associated projects.....	27
7 Dissemination materials.....	29
7.1 Logo and visual style.....	29
7.2 Media Kit.....	29
7.3 Media productions	29
7.4 Further planned dissemination materials.....	29
8 External communication and dissemination activities for Year 1 (M1-M12)	30
8.1 Consultation of the nloVe partners.....	30
8.2 Communication & Dissemination Activities Year 1 (M1-M12).....	30
8.2.1 Website.....	30
8.2.2 Social Media	32
8.2.3 Events.....	34
8.2.4 Publications	35
9 External communication and dissemination activities for Year 2 (M13-M24)	36
9.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities (M13-M18)	36
9.1.1 Website	36
9.1.2 Social Media	37
9.1.3 Dissemination Material.....	38
9.1.4 Events.....	39

9.1.5	Publications	40
9.2	Planned Dissemination and Communication Activities (M19-M24)	40
9.2.1	Website	40
9.2.2	Social Media	40
9.2.3	Dissemination Material.....	40
9.2.4	Events.....	40
9.2.5	Publications	41
10	Communication evaluation and assessment.....	42
11	Conclusions and future work	45

List of Figures

Figure 1: Communication and Dissemination principles	14
Figure 2: nIoVe's Website.....	24
Figure 3: nIoVe's Twitter account.....	25
Figure 4: nIoVe's Facebook Page.....	25
Figure 5: nIoVe's LinkedIn Page.....	26
Figure 6: nIoVe's YouTube Channel.....	26
Figure 7: nIoVe's Logo.....	29
Figure 8: Partner input on dissemination activities.....	30
Figure 9: Homepage of the Website	31
Figure 10: Recent Tweets at Website's HomePage.....	31
Figure 11: Most Visited Paths of nIoVe Website - Year 1	32
Figure 12: Visitors Demographics of nIoVe Website - Year 1.....	32
Figure 13: Homepage Facebook account.....	33
Figure 14: Insights of a post on the LinkedIn account - Year 1.....	33
Figure 15: Tweets - Year 1	34
Figure 16: First Plenary Meeting	35
Figure 17: Latest News - Home Page	36
Figure 18: Page of News.....	37
Figure 19: Facebook - Post Insights.....	37
Figure 20: LinkedIn - Post Insights.....	38
Figure 21: Twitter - Post Insights.....	38
Figure 22: Leaflet - 1st version.....	38
Figure 23: Advanced Cybersecurity Approaches for connected, automated and Electric vehicles.....	39

List of Tables

Table 1: Overview of partners' responsibilities	13
Table 2: Key Stakeholders	19
Table 3: Associated Projects	28
Table 4: Key Statistics for nloVe Project Website - Year 1	32
Table 5: Planned Events - Year 2	41
Table 6: Planned Publications - Year 2	41
Table 7: Dissemination and Communication KPI's	42
Table 8: Identification of KPIs for each Communication Tool - Year1	44

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose, Context and Scope of this Deliverable

nIoVe is a Horizon 2020 project funded by the European Commission's that started on May of 2019. nIoVe draws and builds upon the accumulated experience from its consortium consisted of twelve (12) partners from six (6) European countries and Israel, will implement the project, which is organized in eight (8) work packages and will be completed within thirty-six (36) months (3 years).

The overall goals of nIoVe are to:

- Detect cyber-attacks in real-time while simultaneously preventing them.
- Uptake the innovative cybersecurity solutions for the protection of all CAVs and infrastructure in the IoV network against complex cyber-attacks.
- Identify the risks associated with connected vehicles and IoV networks.
- Recognize and evaluate suspicious threat patterns with the use of advanced Machine Learning (ML) algorithms.
- Enable appropriate coordinated mitigation actions in order to address CAVs safety/security and ensure proper CAVs performance and data management.
- Increase comfort and convenience for passengers.
- Improve road safety and reduce costs.

The overall objectives of nIoVe's project are to:

- Deliver a multi-layered cybersecurity solution for the IoV ecosystem in order to provide protection against wider area of attacks.
- Research and develop a Machine Learning (ML) -Driven Threat Analysis and Situational Awareness Platform for IoV.
- Introduce advanced Visualization and Big Data techniques required for the detection of complex cyber-attacks.
- Introduce a coordinated cyber Incident Smart Response System for CAVs at national & European level.
- Maximize trust between CAVs and infrastructure components through trust management and identification platform.
- Establish and operate a continuously updated and shared Threat Intelligence Repository for CAVs cyber threats to support OEMs and Tier suppliers.
- Support of secure-by-design production lifecycle for all vehicle communications
- Provide cybersecurity solutions to cover execution environments (Smart Cities' infrastructure elements) including all mechanisms (authentication/access control mechanisms, etc.).
- Validate the nIoVe architecture capabilities in proof-of-concept Use Cases.

Work package (WP) 8 aims at (1) raising public awareness of project achievements among the key user groups and stakeholders in the connected-autonomous vehicles and IoV network, the scientific community and the general public; (2) facilitating sharing of knowledge inside the Consortium and establishing the projects' communication & dissemination methodology; (3) developing a business plan for the project tangible outcomes including cost-benefit & cost effectiveness analysis for all project exploitable foreground; (4) identifying challenges and gaps in ongoing connected-autonomous vehicles standardization process and provision of targeted mandates for improving current connected-autonomous vehicles-related standards. In order to achieve the above, the WP consists of four tasks:

Task 8.1 Communication & Dissemination Activities (M1-M36) [Leader: SEEMS (8)]- In this task, initially the communication & dissemination plan of nIoVe will be defined. The plan will contain the procedures and standards to be followed for the communication of project objectives and results as well as the overall strategy for dissemination. A clear communication & dissemination policy will be established early in the project lifetime that will identify the relevant audiences and stakeholders to target along with the appropriate channels to use.

Task 8.2 nIoVe Business Model & Market Analysis for cybersecurity across the IoV (M7-M36) [Leader: HOPU (6)] - Task 8.2 will explore the means to deliver nIoVe outcomes to the market. In parallel to market analysis, the barriers to entry should be determined. A first insight of these barriers will be derived from a specific SWOT analysis. A roadmap will also be conducted among experts, providing deeper knowledge of the factors affecting nIoVe market adoption and evolution.

Task 8.3 IPR Management, Exploitation Strategy & Business Planning (M18-M36) [Leader: HOPU (4)] - This task, in close liaison with all technical WPs (WP3 – WP6) as well as careful worldwide market analysis, will aim at evaluating that the exploitation potential of nIoVe technologies remain the highest.

Task 8.4 – Contribution to IoV Security & Privacy Standardization (M18-M36) [Leader: ICTLC (4)] - This task will initially identify the main standardization bodies and activities for security and privacy in connected-autonomous vehicles and identify gaps and priorities where the nIoVe partners could contribute in an effective way.

1.2 Deliverable Structure

The purpose of the present document is mainly to provide a plan for the effective dissemination and communication of the project results. The present deliverable is split into eleven chapters:

Chapter 1 includes the introduction of the deliverable.

Chapter 2 presents the overall dissemination strategy, the main objectives of nIoVe and the strategy approach.

Chapter 3 provides the communication and dissemination principles.

Chapter 4 includes the identification of the key stakeholders.

Chapter 5 presents a set of tailored messages that target different stakeholders' communities.

Chapter 6 presents all the dissemination channels to be used to reach the targeted groups.

Chapter 7 provides the description of communication tools to be implemented throughout the project process.

Chapter 8 includes the external dissemination and communication activities for Year 1.

Chapter 9 includes the external dissemination and communication activities (executed and planned) for Year 2.

Chapter 10 provides the evaluation and assessment guidelines.

Chapter 11 includes the conclusion and future work.

2 Dissemination and Communication strategy

2.1 Overall objectives

The nIoVe dissemination strategy and activities will ensure that the project outcomes (concepts, scientific results, tools, methodologies, results of validation work, standardization punch-lists, policy and market recommendations) are widely disseminated to the appropriate target communities, at appropriate times and via appropriate methods, and that external stakeholder who can contribute additional value to the development, evaluation, uptake and exploitation of these outcomes can be identified and encouraged to participate.

The main objectives of nIoVe's dissemination and communication activities are:

- Raise public awareness of project achievements among the key user groups and stakeholders in the connected-autonomous vehicles and IoV network, the scientific community, and the general public.
- Facilitate sharing of knowledge inside the Consortium and establishing the projects' communication & dissemination methodology.

Communication activities are an essential part of project dissemination activities, which are designed to inform the general public about the goals and outcomes of nIoVe. The overall communication objectives of the project are:

1. Create Project Identity & Branding
2. Design Dissemination Materials
3. Create Project Website
4. Implement effective social media strategy
5. Networking events and workshops
6. Positive media coverage & releasing publications
7. Cluster with relevant projects & Initiatives

2.2 Strategy Approach

The project's Dissemination & Communication Strategy will be based on a 4-step methodology detailed below, which describes:

1st Step: Why to disseminate?

A high visibility of the project and promotion of an active interaction with key stakeholders are necessary elements to build project awareness. Providing the wider public with advance notice of possible future plans, it also strengthens collaboration links with partners and helps to establish and reinforce a wider networking activity. In other words, it is very crucial to promote the project's results to stakeholders outside the project partnership to ensure that: i) the project outputs will be fully exploited in the most effective manner, i.e. the scaling-up of the demonstrated solutions will be facilitated; ii) the knowledge gained through the project, and more generally the information generated by the project, can be made available to all interested organizations; iii) elements of excellence of the project can be re used and replicated in other projects, becoming a reference point triggering further developments in the field and beyond; v) the project reaches decision-makers to contribute improving future policies and vi) the benefits that the project's outcomes will bring to society are well pointed out.

2nd Step: What to disseminate?

This step concerns the efficient selection of the project information provided for dissemination, on a clear and obvious presentation and on the protection of specific know-how of the project partners so as not to endanger the exploitation of results. Towards this direction, the following project information will be disseminated to the relevant audience: i) Vision (objectives, strategic relevance) and key facts. Since messages will follow an evolution from the start of the project to the aftermath, they will be reviewed periodically in the course of the project, ii) News (achievements and results). Partners will for example recapture how nIoVe project improves people's lives, based on demonstration activities. Personalized experiences will illustrate the impact of the project and will give a human dimension that can catalyze end-user's acceptance, iii) Events promotion and events results. The following project outputs will be disseminated as widely as possible: i) Ready for use solutions, along with lessons-learned and recommendations, ii) Training & Educational sessions on the new tools delivered by the project to respective stakeholders.

3rd Step: What are the target groups for dissemination?

Starting from the pilot countries (France, Slovenia and Greece) where nIoVe technology will be demonstrated, the target sector of the project will be the European Union countries. Both cybersecurity companies and autonomous vehicles manufacturers presence in the project's consortium combined with the demonstration activities will help raising awareness and create a positive momentum around nIoVe. After solidifying the presence in a European level, the next step involves an international expansion, especially in USA who is considered one of the most lucrative regional market. The target groups on which the dissemination and exploitation strategy of the project will be focused are analyzed in chapter 3.

4th Step: How to disseminate?

Given that the targets groups identified cover a wide variety of sectors, from high-level to low-level stakeholders, a different approach-dissemination plan it is needed per target group. At the same time, experience has shown that the usage of the new social media and the web can also play an important role, apart from the dissemination of the project, promoting possible future cooperation but even more providing a real feedback over the circulation of project and a valuable participants' data bank for future projects. The methods and channels will prepare for the scaling-up of the project solutions and will allow for getting the market ready for their use. Communication supports and channels are described below.

The main focus for Year 1 will be to raise awareness on the project's objectives, expected results and general impact, In the second and third year a more targeted approach will be followed, with the aim to create synergies with other similar projects and engage stakeholders more actively.

To ensure effective implementation of the plan, all project partners will be involved in the planned Dissemination and Communication activities, under the guidance of SEEMS, which will ensure that the project activities and results will be widely shared among the identified stakeholders in time and through the most appropriate channels.

2.3 Roles in the consortium

WP8 is led by HOPU but involves all partners in the consortium. The following table gives an overview of the partners' responsibilities and contributions to the main communication and dissemination tasks.

Activity	Responsibilities
Dissemination and communication activities (Overall)	SEEMS supported by all partners
Input to nloVe's Website	SEEMS supported by all partners
Input to nloVe's social media	SEEMS supported by all partners
Update of Dissemination and communication plan	SEEMS supported by all partners
Coordination of Press Release	SEEMS in collaboration with CERTH
Newsletters	SEEMS in collaboration with CERTH
Dissemination Material	SEEMS in collaboration with CERTH
Organization of Project Events & Collaboration with Stakeholders	SEEMS in collaboration with CERTH and supported by all partners
Connection with other initiatives	CERTH supported by all partners
Publications	All partners
Share project results to social media	All partners

Table 1: Overview of partners' responsibilities

3 Communication and dissemination principles

3.1 General Principles

Traditional and modern tools and dissemination actions will be implemented in accordance with the communication principles and the priorities that have been set during the design and development phase of the project. In order to ensure maximum efficiency and impact the dissemination and communication plan is based on the following principles:

Figure 1: Communication and Dissemination principles

1. nloVe's communication strategy is important to be flexible in order to adapt to the changing needs and challenges of the target groups and the environment that takes place.
2. Existing Synergies will be exploited to reach key audiences and avoid a duplication of effort.
3. To achieve maximum efficiency and impact to all target audiences, the project will create core messages tailored to the different target audiences while expressed in a relative context.
4. The communication strategy will cover the entire project but will adapt to cover the different key audiences.

3.2 EU Communication Rules

This section lists the communication and dissemination rules that must be followed by the participants of an EU Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, as presented in the Grant Agreement, the consortium agreement and the relevant EU documents of "Horizon 2020".

3.2.1 Obligation to disseminate results

Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible 'disseminate' its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests. If a beneficiary intends not to protect its results, it may — under certain conditions (see Article 26.4.1) — need to formally notify the Commission before dissemination takes place.

3.2.2 Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

In particular, it must:

- (a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications.
- (b) Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.
- (c) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:
 - (i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or
 - (ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.
- (d) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

3.2.3 Open access to research data

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action (‘data’), the beneficiaries must:

- (a) deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:
 - (i) the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible.
 - (ii) not applicable.
 - (iii) other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the ‘data management plan’.
- (b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of

their research data under Point (a) (i) and (iii), if the achievement of the action's main objective (as described in Annex 1) would be jeopardized by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible.

In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.

3.2.4 Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

(c) display the EU emblem and

(d) include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 833742”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission.

This does not however give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

3.2.5 Disclaimer excluding Commission responsibility

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

3.2.6 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43).

Such a breach may also lead to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

4 Stakeholder Communities

The most crucial goal of nIoVe's dissemination strategy is to identify the key target groups who will contribute to the project and influence its success.

It is essential to understand these stakeholders since each have different expectations from the project and different communication needs. Each stakeholder category has a different level of power in influencing, communication reach or decision making. In this context, the stakeholders which are more important to reach and engage must be identified appropriately in order to assist with the dissemination of the project results to the right audience. Dissemination channels and materials must be created and developed accordingly to achieve maximum impact.

The key stakeholders identified for the nIoVe project are:

- Vehicle Manufacturers
- Designers of post-market devices for CAVs
- Cybersecurity Companies
- Transportation authorities and Transport service providers
- Smart Cities and Governments
- Passengers and pedestrians
- Scientific Community
- Standardization bodies
- Policy making/support bodies

The following table provides an overview of the stakeholder's description, importance and means to reach them.

Stakeholder Group	Description	Importance	To be reached through the following channels:
Vehicle Manufacturers	The vehicle manufactures - from IoV and CAVs perspective – design and develop innovative, smart, and sustainable mobility solutions, including driverless and automated vehicles used for the first and the last mile transportation	High	- Website/social media - training seminars, - leaflets - demonstrations
Designers of post-market devices for CAVs	The designers of post-market devices - from IoV and CAVs perspective – design and develop devices for CAVs such as GPS, radar, odometers, GNSS base, lidar, video camera, inertial measurement unit (IMUs), and	High	- Website/social media - training seminars, - leaflets - demonstrations

	embedded electronics like engine control units (ECUs) in order to extract, receive or send, save and analyze useful data from the inner and outer environment of a vehicle.		
Cybersecurity Companies	An important target group of the nIoVe solution is comprised of security companies, which wish to exploit on the project's results and enrich their existing technologies.	High	- Website/social media
Transportation authorities and Transport service providers	This target group includes transport authorities and service provider's enterprises that need cyber risks management, information on cybersecurity landscape, and anomaly detection and will be willing of becoming future customers.	High	- Website/social media - leaflets - demonstrations
Smart Cities and Governments	Residential and Commercial end-user's, including smart city's authorities can benefit of nIoVe's results. These authorities are a major stakeholder in the IoV domain who collect live data from the connected (autonomous) vehicles and provide them useful information like traffic conditions, diversions, etc.	High	- Website/social media - leaflets - demonstrations
Passengers and pedestrians	Passengers and pedestrians are among the main sources of the personal data that can be involved in processing activities and as such their role in	Medium to High	- Website/social media

	the CAV environment must be considered with respect to compliance with data protection provisions in addition to the necessity to have appropriate organizational and technical security measures in place.		
Scientific Community	This target group corresponds to research and academic organizations, scientific journals, committees, internet fora, and other working groups in research fields related to the nloVe work.	Medium to High	- Website/social media
Standardization bodies	They form an essential target group of the project dissemination and exploitation activities.	Medium to High	- Website/social media
Policy making/support bodies are	A critical target group for the exploitation of the project results and realization of the long-term impact of the project.	High	- Website/social media

Table 2: Key Stakeholders

The categories with high importance shape the major shareholder groups that are directly interested in nloVe's advances. Consequently, the approach to communication will be tailored to their needs and expectations in order to take advantage of their specificities for maximum effect and engage them to future collaboration.

The stakeholders list will be assessed and updated on a regular basis during the project. The stakeholder engagement strategy will be also assessed and updated based on continuous feedback from all communication activities of the project.

5 Tailored messages

A major challenge faced in any research project regarding the dissemination of its result is to communicate the right message to the right audience. For that purpose, a set of configurable messages that target different stakeholders' categories are presented below.

5.1 General message

The general message is used to describe the project. It will be used in all dissemination materials.

nIoVe aims to deploy a novel multi-layered interoperable cybersecurity solution for the Internet-of-Vehicles (IoV), with emphasis of the Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) ecosystem by employing an advanced cybersecurity system enabling all relevant stakeholders and incident response teams to share cyber threat intelligence, synchronize and coordinate their cybersecurity strategies, response and recovery activities. To do so the project develops a set of in-vehicle and V2X data collectors that will feed nIoVe's machine learning platform and tools for threat analysis and situational awareness across the IoV ecosystem. Advanced visual and data analytics are further enhanced and adapted to boost cyberthreat detection performance under complex attack scenarios, while IoV stakeholders are jointly engaged in incident response activities through trusted mechanisms. The proposed approach is supported by interoperable data exchange between existing and newly proposed cybersecurity tools.

5.2 Extended general message

For more specific audiences a supplementary description to the general message will be provided. This description will also be displayed in the project's website.

nIoVe aims to deploy a novel multi-layered interoperable cybersecurity solution for the Internet-of-Vehicles (IoV), with emphasis of the Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) ecosystem by employing an advanced cybersecurity system enabling all relevant stakeholders and incident response teams to share cyber threat intelligence, synchronize and coordinate their cybersecurity strategies, response and recovery activities. To do so the project develops a set of in-vehicle and V2X data collectors that will feed nIoVe's machine learning platform and tools for threat analysis and situational awareness across the IoV ecosystem. Advanced visual and data analytics are further enhanced and adapted to boost cyberthreat detection performance under complex attack scenarios, while IoV stakeholders are jointly engaged in incident response activities through trusted mechanisms. The proposed approach is supported by interoperable data exchange between existing and newly proposed cybersecurity tools. nIoVe solution will be demonstrated and validated in 3 pilots: Hybrid execution environment, simulated environment and real-world conditions. Overall, nIoVe ambitiously expects to (i) reduce the attack surface of the overall IoV ecosystem, (ii) showcase effective and real-time detection of novel advanced threats and cyber-attacks in IoV ecosystems; (iii) reduce substantially the response time and reduce drastically the impact of breaches; (iv) contribute to the establishment and sustainable operation of Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs) stimulating information and knowledge sharing across the IoV ecosystem; and (v) paves the way for the next generation robust, scalable and resilient IoV infrastructure. nIoVe draws and builds upon the accumulated experience from its consortium consisted of 12 partners from 6 European countries and Israel, will implement the project, which is organized in 8 work packages and will be completed within 36 months.

5.3 Scientific and educational message

This message refers to the scientific and educational community and provides mainly the technical results of the project.

Today's vehicles are increasingly "connected"; there is wireless data exchange with servers, infrastructure, and other vehicles. Tomorrow's vehicles will be automated and autonomous, capable of sensing their environment and navigating through cities without human input. Therefore, Connected, as well as Autonomous Vehicles stand to introduce new enablers in mobility and transport, however this comes with the cost of a new set of threats pertaining to higher risks of cyber-attacks. A cyber-attack in a Connected and Autonomous Vehicle (CAV) can yield high recall costs, loss of property and even jeopardize human safety. Therefore, the need for cyber protection of CAVs is becoming paramount. nIoVe project is going to deliver a holistic and multi-layered cybersecurity solution for the Internet-of-Vehicles (IoV) by addressing secure-by-design aspects of CAVs, along with cyber protection, threat response and attack recovery at vehicle, infrastructure and service/ application layer of the whole IoV ecosystem at complex use cases. nIoVe project is making a step-change in Europe in bringing down the number of fatalities, reducing harmful emissions from transport work and reducing congestion within urban environments. The aim of nIoVe is to detect cyber-attacks in real-time while simultaneously preventing them. Regarding the automotive market, nIoVe purpose to uptake the innovative cybersecurity solutions for the protection of all CAVs and infrastructure in the IoV network against complex cyber-attacks.

The nIoVe cybersecurity reference framework for CAVs and Internet-of-Vehicles (IoV) network will be built upon an enhanced Cybersecurity platform for passengers of CAVs and Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEMs) of CAVs. This will give the opportunity to a) identify the risks associated with connected of vehicles and IoV networks, b) recognize and evaluate suspicious threat patterns with the use of advanced Machine Learning (ML) algorithms, and finally c) to enable appropriate coordinated mitigation actions in order to address CAVs safety/security and ensure proper CAVs performance and data management. Additionally, nIoVe can offer (near) real time detection of anomalies, as well as can response against evolving complex cyber-attack and successfully recovery. Furthermore, nIoVe will increase the OEMs readiness level and the effectiveness of the automation of existing cybersecurity services and will open up the cybersecurity 'Blackbox' to connected and autonomous vehicles. In this context, it will build trust through coordinated assessment but also drive forward security-by-design and privacy mechanisms that are needed to guarantee the smooth and reliable operation of CAVs.

Keywords: Complex cyber-attacks; communication networks; Connected and autonomous vehicles; detection; response; recovery; shared threat information; machine learning; Internet of Vehicles.

5.4 Message for the general public

This kind of message is addressed to the general public. The wording is simpler so that the message is understood by audiences with no technical background.

Today's vehicles are increasingly "connected"; there is wireless data exchange with servers, infrastructure, and other vehicles. Tomorrow's vehicles will be automated and autonomous, capable of sensing their environment and navigating through cities without human input. Therefore, Connected, as well as Autonomous Vehicles stand to introduce new enablers in mobility and transport, however this comes with the cost of a new set of threats pertaining to higher risks of cyber-attacks. A cyber-attack in a Connected and Autonomous Vehicle (CAV) can yield high recall costs, loss of property and even jeopardize human safety. Therefore, the need

for cyber protection of CAVs is becoming paramount. The aim of nIoVe is to detect cyber-attacks in real-time while simultaneously preventing them. In this way, the project demonstrates the benefits of early detection and response against of cyber-attacks for the secure and safe operation of CAVs and encourages automotive manufacturers (OEMs, Tier suppliers, etc.) to integrate shielding mechanisms to their vehicles increasing vehicle resiliency and owner safety. nIoVe project is making a step-change in Europe in bringing down the number

of fatalities, reducing harmful emissions from transport work and reducing congestion within urban environments.

It is noted that the above messages are an early attempt to reach the target audience. Customized messages representing the areas of interest of each partner separately should be created.

6 Communication channels

One of the major challenges of nloVe project is to properly engage all the communities of stakeholders mentioned above. This implies that nloVe needs to support communication and dissemination activities which, with the appropriate technique, will meet the needs of each of the research community.

The various information tools that will be implemented by the project participants are considered important as they will provide an additional dimension to disseminate the nloVe's objectives and develop solutions. The central point in this direction is expected to be the project site, along with the various social media channels. Additionally, posts, articles and press releases will also be produced throughout the project and distributed in order to reach extended audiences and broaden the project's impact.

All members involved in the project will need to provide the necessary input to this challenge.

6.1 Website

The project website will be the main tool for communication and dissemination activities during project implementation. It will be also used to republish material that is shared on any social media channel of the project or other communication channel used by the project partners. In addition, all project deliverables, newsletters, multimedia, and related articles will be posted on the website.

The website of nloVe's project is hosted at <http://www.niove.eu>. The website has been developed to manage the project's content at two levels: 1. External communication and dissemination of the project results and achievements and 2. Internal on-line collaboration between the partners.

The website includes the project description, prospects, news & events related to the nloVe topics and announcements. The project website also includes a usable content management system (i.e. in the form of Wiki), where partners can put articles about intermediate project results. Furthermore, it will contain public documents (i.e. project publications) available for download. Links to other relevant sites such as nloVe partners relevant projects, relevant EC sites, cyber-security platforms etc. The website will allow on-line collaboration between partners that includes exchange of documents and support for discussion lists, and a calendar with information about forthcoming events and tasks (workshops, meetings, and deadlines). All the intermediate results of the project (internal management/progress reports, deliverables, presentations, papers, data sets, software, etc.) will be available to the partners through this website.

In more details, the website consists of a homepage with the aim of giving a general description of the project, the participants in the consortium, but also the latest news in headlines. Detailed news related to the program and any event are posted separately in the "News" section. In the "Organization" section the structure of the project as well as the work packages with the deliverables in a detailed description can be found in detail. There is a section titled "Dissemination" and "Outreach" that include dissemination actions and communication of the project. Finally, the "Contact" section provides the general public with the opportunity to resolve any question regarding the project by completing a corresponding form or contacting the project coordinator directly.

Figure 2: nIoVe's Website

One of the main goals of creating the project website is to have a constant presence over the Internet and engage the target audience. The website content will be constantly enriched. The addition of multimedia content is the next step.

The hosting, maintenance and update of the website is SEEMS responsibility. All partners will be responsible to enrich the website's content with relevant dissemination material (e.g. news, publications, deliverables, multimedia etc.).

6.2 Social networks

One powerful tool to enhance the project's communication strategy is to establish its presence in social media networks. The main goal is to engage the key audience by providing regular and interesting content.

- **Twitter account:** <https://twitter.com/NioveProject>
- **Facebook account:** <https://www.facebook.com/NioveProject/>
- **LinkedIn account:** <https://www.linkedin.com/in/nioveproject/>
- **YouTube:** https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCuwSjBWhPwquB-Mxlr_XQGA?view_as=subscriber

A **Twitter account** has been created showing all actions and events during the implementation of the program. Through this account, the project is planning to disseminate short and simple content for the wider public.

Figure 3: nIoVe's Twitter account

A Facebook Page has also been setup. This account will include posts, shares, videos and every other element related to the communication strategy of the project.

Figure 4: nIoVe's Facebook Page

A LinkedIn account has been created in order to attract the attention from researchers and the industrial stakeholders.

Figure 5: nIoVe's LinkedIn Page

A **YouTube Channel** has been created in order to provide a single place of all nIoVe videos. It is the appropriate place where the consortium can post relevant videos explaining the activities that take place during the implementation of the project.

Figure 6: nIoVe's YouTube Channel

One of the main goals of creating the project social media is to raise awareness and engage the target audience. The content will be constantly enriched. All partners will be responsible to enrich the content with relevant dissemination material (e.g. news, publications, multimedia etc.).

6.3 (Joint-) events

nIoVe will support different International Conferences, forums, events. In addition, it will develop specialized workshops to attract the community, share ideas, and present the results from the project.

Such events will be organized to support SMEs, entrepreneurs and end-users via hackathons, meet-ups and other activities, in order to make sure that the emerging market for the CAVs will be benefited and aware of nIoVe benefits, usability and how it works. SEEMS, will also contribute to the promotion of nIoVe with a closing event open to the public at the European Parliament, which will present results and outcomes of the project to policymakers.

6.4 Newsletters

Newsletters will be prepared and published on a periodic basis during the project. These will include information about the project status and progress, planned dissemination and communication activities (participation to events, publications etc.), their results as well as an assessment of the project achievements.

6.5 Resources available via associated projects

nIoVe's project is connect to European R&D projects with major organizations. The consortium will seek to collaborate under H2020.

Name of project	Description	Represented in nIoVe
AVENUE	Autonomous Vehicles to Evolve to a New Urban Experience(2017:ART-07-2017): The AVENUE project aims to translate the technical evolutions, operational and behavioural challenges, into a successful integrated autonomous public transportation service, adapted for the needs of passengers and to city strategies and urban development planning. (Participants: UniGe, NAVYA, TPG, CERTH)	UniGe
		NAVYA
		TPG
		CERTH
SerIoT	Secure and Safe IoT (2018:H2020-IOT-3-2017): Focuses on the identification and design of security and privacy solutions for the IoT. The research areas include IoT Oriented Honeypots & statistical signal analysis of IoT devices and traffic, Blockchain on IoT (Participants: CERTH)	CERTH
GHOST	Safe-Guarding Home IoT Environments with Personalised Realtime Risk Control (2017: H2020-DS-SC7-2016): GHOST deploys a software solution for smart-homes and brings professional level security to the citizen and to this end it. (Participants: CERTH, UniGe)	CERTH
		UniGe
SPIRIT	Security and Privacy for the Internet of Things (2016:CHISTERA): The SPIRIT project will investigate the Proof-of Concept of employing novel secure and privacy-ensuring techniques in services set-up in the Internet of Things (IoT) environment, aiming to increase the trust of users in IoT-based systems. (Participants: UniGe)	UniGe
KONFIDO	Secure and Trusted Paradigm for Interoperable eHealth Services (2016:H2020-DS-SC1-2016 RIA): KONFIDO advances the state of the art of eHealth technology with respect to 4 key dimensions of digital security: data preservation, access, modification, exchange, interoperability & compliance (Participants: CERTH)	CERTH
PaaSWord	A Holistic Data Privacy & Security by Design Platform-as-a Service Framework Introducing Distributed Encrypted Persistence in Cloud-	RISE

	based Applications. (2015:H2020-ICT-2014-1): PaaSword introduced a holistic data privacy and security by design framework enhanced by sophisticated context-aware policy access models and robust policy access, decision, enforcement, and enabled the implementation of secure and transparent Cloud-based applications. (Participants: RISE)	
5G-ENSURE	5G Enablers for Network and System Security and Resilience (2015: H2020-ICT-2014-2): 5G-ENSURE will define and deliver a 5G Security Architecture, shared and agreed by the various 5G stakeholders. (Participants: RISE)	<i>RISE</i>
CARMEL	CARMEL's goal is to proactively address modern vehicle cybersecurity challenges applying advanced Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques and also to continuously seek methods to mitigate associated safety risks. (Close collaboration of ATHENA with CARMEL's consortium)	<i>ATHENA</i>
SecureIoT	SecureIoT aims to bring certificate-based security to resource-constrained IoT. RISE is the technical project leader and main contributor to the technology development.	<i>RISE</i>

Table 3: Associated Projects

7 Dissemination materials

The dissemination and communication activities will be implemented throughout the project process. The nIoVe results will be used for dissemination and exploitation activities by the consortium partners during and after the end of the project.

7.1 Logo and visual style

One of the first steps during the implementation of the project was to create a recognizable logo, which design is based on simplicity and bright colours. This logo gives a solid identity and is used by participants in all deliverables, presentations and social media. In short, it is a key element of marketing and is used in any research, communication and dissemination activity throughout the project implementation.

Figure 7: nIoVe's Logo

7.2 Media Kit

An information media kit and project press releases will be developed. The media kit will include brochures, presentations, and multimedia content. Press releases will be published when significant results of project implementation have been achieved.

7.3 Media productions

nIoVe's consortium believes that through a multimedia approach the project results will reach and engage a wider audience. The multimedia will demonstrate the nIoVe's solution, its applications, features and benefits. A short film will be produced one year to 6 months before the end of the project in order to make the project understandable for the public.

7.4 Further planned dissemination materials

The planned materials to be created include: a) A short project film (3-5 minutes); b) An electronic newsletter c) A project brochure presenting project objectives, expected results and profiles of partners; d) A project Fact Sheet, which will be widely disseminated by the EC, e) Official project templates: a journalistic description of the project understandable for the public, a PowerPoint presentation will be prepared to promote project concept and innovations.

8 External communication and dissemination activities for Year 1 (M1-M12)

The first action taken in order to promote the project concerns the preparation of the communication and dissemination plan. The basic role of this section is to summarize all the dissemination activities performed by the partners of nloVe in the 1st year of the project (1st May 2019 to 30th April 2020). The dissemination activities are separated in categories according to their content.

8.1 Consultation of the nloVe partners

In context of the "Dissemination and Communication Plan" preparation, an excel file has been prepared to record the dissemination and communication activities of the project.

All partners were requested to provide relevant information about the following:

- Planned nloVe-related publications,
- Planned nloVe-related events and networking activities,
- Established dissemination channels (such as publications, website, social media, etc.).

Partner	Place	Start Date	End Date	Event Name	Type of Event	Type of contribution	Details (title of presentation)
ICTLC	Brussels, Belgium	22-Jan-20	24-Jan-20	CPDP 2020	Conference	Oral Presentation	Lectures
ICTLC	Lisbon, Portugal	10/02/2020	14/02/2020	Data Protection Officer (DPO) Certification courses	Course	Oral Presentation	Lectures
ICTLC	Brussels, Belgium	09/03/2020	13/03/2020	Data Protection Officer (DPO) Certification courses	Course	Oral Presentation	Lectures
ICTLC	Maastricht, The Netherlands	29/06/2020	03/07/2020	Data Protection Officer (DPO) Certification courses	Course	Oral Presentation	Lectures
ICTLC	Maastricht, The Netherlands	23/03/2020	27/03/2020	Privacy Executive week	Course	Oral Presentation	Lectures
TUM	Germany	01/05/20		System Design for the IoT, Software architectures for distributed embedded systems	Lectures and Exerci	Lectures and TUM ESI webs	Communication of nloVe activities
TPG	Geneva			Publicity TPG bus	Publicity	Video	TPG in motion
TPG	Geneva			Internal communication	Article	Article	Connected autonomous vehicle
TPG	Geneva			University project presentation	Article	Article	Connected autonomous vehicle
TPG	Geneva			Public Authorities presentation	Presentation	Article or Oral Presentation	Connected autonomous vehicle
ATHENA	Poland	04/09/2019	06/09/2019	1st IEEE Conference on Societal Automation	Scientific Conference	Oral Presentation	The article "Complex Engineering enabler for security in Internet Of Presentation entitled: "Internet of security challenges: the nloVe Pro
ATHENA	Greece	23/11/2019	24/11/2019	22nd Development Forum/Money Show Patras	Development & Inno	Oral Presentation	

Figure 8: Partner input on dissemination activities

Partner are requested to update the file regularly in order to record all dissemination activities and have in one file all implemented and planned dissemination activities and channels.

8.2 Communication & Dissemination Activities Year 1 (M1-M12)

This section presents the Communication & Dissemination activities that took place during the first year of the project. The dissemination of the project through the website and social media is described in detail. Also, the communication and dissemination activities of the project are presented as carried out by each member of the consortium.

8.2.1 Website

The current view of the project's webpage is presented in Figure 9. Throughout the first year, the content of the page was updated with news of the project, including images and links and any material related to the dissemination of the project. Social Media posts were also displayed in the Home Page. An upgraded section of "Latest News" and website features for disabled users has have been recently added.

The specifications and the structure of the project’s website is provided in the deliverable D8.3, in detail.

---About nIoVe project---

nIoVe project is making a step-change in Europe in bringing down the number of fatalities, reducing harmful emissions from transport work and reducing congestion within urban environments. The aim of nIoVe is to **detect cyber-attacks in realtime while simultaneously preventing them**. Regarding the **automotive market**, nIoVe **purpose to uptake the innovative cybersecurity solutions for the protection of all CAVs and infrastructure in the IoV network** against complex cyber-attacks. [Read more](#)

Figure 9: Homepage of the Website

Figure 10: Recent Tweets at Website’s HomePage

Google analytics are used to analyze the KPIs and adjust the website accordingly. Google Analytics is one of the leading and most powerful tools for monitoring and analyzing "traffic" on a Website. It provides a huge amount of information about who visited the website, what the visitors searched for and how they arrived on the website. The usefulness of Google Analytics is very important.

The key statistics of the project’s webpage are presented in Table 4. The most visited pages are the "Project", the "Home" and the "Partners" page (See Figure 11). Regarding the demographic data of the visitors, the majority of them come from Greece, followed by Germany and USA (See Figure 12).

nIoVe Project Website Statistics-Year1	
Users	251
Page Views	1.074
Sessions	404
Average Session Duration	1m 52s

Table 4: Key Statistics for nIoVe Project Website - Year 1

Page	Pageviews
/	384
/index.php/project	186
/index.php	106
/index.php/partners	103
/index.php/organization	57
/index.php/outreach	55
/index.php/dissemination	46
/index.php/dissemination/publications	46
/index.php/10-news/10-kom	24
/index.php/dissemination/talks	24

Figure 11: Most Visited Paths of nIoVe Website - Year 1

Sessions by country

Figure 12: Visitors Demographics of nIoVe Website - Year 1

8.2.2 Social Media

An important part of the communication and implementation strategy of the project is the definition of its presence and the regular updating of the content on social networks. The project's social media accounts are a major means of dissemination. Equally on Facebook, on LinkedIn and Twitter, the public can find project-related announcements. These accounts are updated at the same time as the project website.

8.2.2.1 Facebook

The Facebook profile was created at the same time as the website during the first month of the project (See Figure 13). The purpose of creating this profile is to attract the main audience by providing regular and interesting content.

Figure 13: Homepage Facebook account

The LinkedIn account was created on M1 during the project. The account is used to link the project to other similar ones operating in the same areas of technology. Each post provides information about the demographics of the project account visitors (See Figure 14). This helps to form a complete picture of the audience the project attracts and to adapt the content of the project’s posts according to the desired network of stakeholders.

Figure 14: Insights of a post on the LinkedIn account - Year 1

8.2.2.2 Twitter

The Twitter account was created along with the project website during the first month. In the first year, on Twitter, posts included news, meetings and announcements of various actions that mentioned the project (See Figure 15). Many of Niove's Tweets have been retweeted both to partner accounts and to companies or organizations operating in the same fields. In the first year, the account gained 30 followers and gained 534 impressions. We expect the numbers of tweets, fans, and impressions to increase during the second year.

Figure 15: Tweets - Year 1

8.2.3 Events

Below the events that took place during the first year of the project are displayed:

8.2.3.1 Presentations

- RISE- Presentation at the RISE-Ericsson Annual Security Day event 2019, Seminar, Stockholm-Sweden, 10/02/2019.
- ATHENA- Presentation in the 22nd Development Forum/Money Show Patras, Greece, 23/11/2019-24/11/2019.
- ICTLC- NGIoT Webinar: Data Protection in the transport field: IoT, IoV and Crime Prevention, Webinar, 25/02/2020.
- KENOTOM- Video: Embedded World 2020, Exhibition, 25/02/2020.
- ICTLC- Oral Presentation- Data Protection Officer (DPO) Certification courses, Brussels- Belgium, 09/03/2020.
- ICTLC- Oral Presentation- Oral Presentation-Privacy Executive week, Maastricht-The Netherlands, 23/03/2020.
- ICTLC- Oral Presentation-Oral Presentation- Annual Privacy Forum 2020, Lisbon-Portugal, 06/04/2020.
- TUM-Lecture "System Design for the IoT, Software architectures for distributed embedded systems", Germany, 01/05/2020.

8.2.3.2 Consortium Meetings

- Kick-off Meeting

The Kick-Off Meeting of nIoVe's project was held in CERTH, Thessaloniki during the 20th-21st of May 2019.

The project organizational structure, work packages, tasks and deliverables were presented and described. The partners introduced their organizations and described their role in the project.

The next meeting of the Consortium was held in Göteborg, Sweden in September 2019.

➤ 1st Plenary Meeting

The first plenary meeting of nloVe project took place at RISE Institutes of Sweden on the 2nd and 3rd of September. The partners discussed the main activities to be completed by the end of the 1st year of the project. At the end of the meeting and after a good collaboration between the partners, the consortium had an overview of the project deliverables activities.

The next meeting was held in Paris, France in November 2019.

Figure 16: First Plenary Meeting

➤ Technical Meeting

The nloVe technical meeting took place in Paris on the 22/11/2020. The agenda of this meeting included the update of technical requirements, the clarification of system architecture and discussion for potential technical issues in the development phase.

8.2.4 Publications

In this subchapter, the scientific publications created during the first year of implementation of the project are presented, in detail:

[1] Angeliki Zacharaki, Ioannis Paliokas, Konstantinos Votis, Christos Alexakos, Dimitrios Serpanos and Dimitrios Tzovaras, “**Complex Engineering Systems as an enabler for security in Internet of Vehicles: The nloVe approach**”, IEEE Societal Automation 2019 (SA2019), (in press).

[2] Mudassar Aslam, Simon Bouget, Shahid Raza, “**Security and Trust Preserving Inter- and Intra-Cloud VM Migrations**”, International Journal of Network Management, 17 February 2020.

9 External communication and dissemination activities for Year 2 (M13-M24)

9.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities (M13-M18)

During the second year, the communication and dissemination strategy envisages the strengthening of activities to improve the results and increase their impact on the dissemination of the project. Below the activities carried out during the first six months of the second year are described in detail followed by the planned activities of each participant for the remaining six months of the second year.

9.1.1 Website

The fact that the dissemination activities started to intensify during the first half of the second year, led to the need to improve the structure of the website. Moreover, the section of the "Latest News" (See Figure 17) was upgraded both on the Home page and on the "News" page (See Figure 18). In this way, visitors can be informed directly about all the actions related to the nloVe project.

Figure 17: Latest News - Home Page

Figure 18: Page of News

9.1.2 Social Media

In the first twelve months, Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter were the main tools for the communication and dissemination of the project. The goal from the beginning of the second year is to strengthen the audience reaction on the Social Media posts. This can be performed by continuously evaluating the statistics (See Figures 19, 20, 21), to effectively target the key audience.

Figure 19: Facebook - Post Insights

Figure 20: LinkedIn - Post Insights

Figure 21: Twitter - Post Insights

9.1.3 Dissemination Material

A leaflet was created for general purpose use.

Figure 22: Leaflet - 1st version

9.1.4 Events

Below the events that took place during the first half of the second year of the project are displayed:

9.1.4.1 Presentations

- ICTLC - Data Protection Officer (DPO) Certification courses, Maastricht-The Netherlands 26/06/2020-03/07/2020.
- CERTH - CyberSec: Advanced Cybersecurity Approaches for Connected, Automated and Electric Vehicles, Greece, September 2020.
- ATHENA, CERTH : EWGT2020: 23rd EURO Working Group on Transportation, 2TC1: Cybersecurity of Connected and Automated Vehicles (Special Session) 3rd EURO Working Group on Transportation, Paphos-Cyprus, 18/09/2020-19/09/2020.

9.1.4.2 Consortium Meetings

- 2nd Plenary Meeting

The second plenary meeting of nloVe project took place on the 5th and 6th of May 2020. The partners discussed the main activities that were completed by the end of the 1st year of the project. The main technical achievements were introduced, and the partners decided about the next steps of the project.

9.1.4.3 Workshops

- Designing Connected and Automated Vehicles around Legal and Ethical Concerns – Data Protection as a Corporate Social Responsibility : Paolo Balboni, Martim Taborada Barata, Anastasia Botsi & Kate Francis of ICT Legal Consulting participated in the Workshop on AI, Law and Ethics on September 3, 2020, hosted by the 11th Hellenic Conference on Artificial Intelligence special events section. The panel talked about the nloVe Project during the presentation.
- Advanced Cybersecurity Approaches for Connected, Automated and Electric Vehicles: On Sunday 20/9/2020 (9:00 - 16:00 EEST), the workshop "Advanced Cybersecurity Approaches for connected, automated and electric vehicles" (<https://cybersec-itsc2020.isi.gr/>) was organized on the framework of the 23rd IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems. The workshop included only invited speeches from EU projects (nloVe, CAMEL, SAFERtec, 2CeVau, CONCORDIA), ENISA, Renault and ETSI.

Figure 23: Advanced Cybersecurity Approaches for connected, automated and Electric vehicles

9.1.5 Publications

In this subchapter, the scientific publications created during the months M13-M18 of the project are presented in detail:

[1] Alexakos C., Katsini C., Votis K., Lalas A., Tzovaras D., Serpanos D, **“Enabling Digital Forensics Readiness for Internet of Vehicles”**, 23rd EURO Working Group on Transportation Meeting, EWGT 2020, 16-18 September 2020, Paphos, Cyprus).

[2] Mohammad Hamad, Zain A. H. Hammadeh, Selma Saidi, Vassilis Prevelakis, **“Temporal-Based Intrusion Detection for IoV”**, Information Technology (submitted).

[3] Anastasia Theodouli, Konstantinos Moschou, Konstantinos Votis, Dimitrios Tzovaras, Jan Lauinger, Sebastian Steinhorst, **“Towards a Blockchain-based Identity and Trust Management Framework for the IoV Ecosystem”**, 2020 Global Internet of Things Summit (GloTS), 03/06/2020.

9.2 Planned Dissemination and Communication Activities (M19-M24)

The planned communication and dissemination activities for M19-M24 are presented below:

9.2.1 Website

- Enrich the website with multimedia
- Increase visitors
- Add dissemination material

9.2.2 Social Media

- Increase the number of followers
- Regular updates
- Increase engagement of all partners

9.2.3 Dissemination Material

- Publish Press Release
- Publish Newsletter
- Create video

9.2.4 Events

Participation in external events (conferences, workshops, symposia) are considered a great opportunity to gain direct contact with the industrial and research communities so they must be planned very carefully.

nIoVe outputs will be disseminated as widely as possible: **i) Ready for use solutions, along with lessons-learned and recommendations, ii) Training & Educational sessions on the new tools delivered by the project to respective stakeholders.**

The following table (Table 5) presents by category the communication and dissemination activities of the project for the second year, as planned by each participant separately.

Partner	Place	Date	Event Name	Type of Activity	Type of contribution
HOPU	Malaga (Spain)	30/09/2020-10/01/2020	Technologies for Smart Cities	Conference: Green Cities	Presentation
HOPU	Dublin	To be determined	IoT for cities and Industry	Conference: IoT-Week	Presentation

HOPU	Barcelona	17/11/2020-20/11/2020	IoT for cities	Conference: Smart City Expo World Congress	Presentation
ATHENA CERTH	On-line or part of a conference	2021	Workshop: Advanced Cybersecurity Approaches for Connected, Automated and Electric Vehicles	Workshop	Oral Presentation
TUM		2020-2021	System Design for the IoT, Software architectures for distributed embedded systems		

Table 5: Planned Events - Year 2

9.2.5 Publications

The next table (Table 6) presents in detail the publications that have been planned for the second year.

Publication Title	Published In	Date	Partner
Enabling Digital Forensics Readiness for Internet of Vehicles	IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computing	Estimated in 2021	ATHENA
Attack attribution and forensics analysis for Internet of Vehicles	IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics	Estimated in 2021	ATHENA
Modelling Plans for Digital Forensics Readiness	IEEE ETFA2021 Conference	Estimated in 2021	ATHENA
Importance of cybersecurity	NGI Community	During 2020	HOPU
Methodology for Quantitative System-Level Security Verification of the IoV Infrastructure	IEEE IoT journal	July 2020	TUM- RISE
Paper 1	SAC21 conference	October - 2020	TUM
Paper 2	DATE21 conference	October - 2020	TUM
TBD	Plan to be submitted to Sensors journal	February 2021	TUM - CERTH
TBD	Plan to be submitted ACM Transactions on Internet of Things	January 2021	TUM

Table 6: Planned Publications - Year 2

10 Communication evaluation and assessment

All dissemination and communication activities will be closely monitored to ensure the success of the plan. The effectiveness of the nlOve's communication and dissemination strategy will be periodically evaluated during the three (3) years of implementation. All partners play an important role in the implementation of the plan and in providing feedback to achieve maximum impact.

The communication and the dissemination plan's effectiveness will be evaluated base on KPIs that have been set for the total duration of the project.

Comm. Objective	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Create Project Identity & Branding	Create project branding and identity. Final Logo and colour scheme.	Revise Branding and Identity as required by project partners.	Revise Branding and Identity as required by project partners.
Design Dissemination Materials	Publicity materials: leaflet/ brochure, poster & other.	Update materials according to progress.	Update materials according to project progress.
Create Project Website	Launch website (project overview, communication platform).	Update the website with portal information and open data repository.	Update open data repository and add access to the nlOve platform.
Implement effective social media strategy	YouTube – Video live w. 1000 hits Facebook – 400 followers Twitter – 360 tweets, 150 followers.	YouTube – 3 Videos live w. 2000 hits Facebook – 800 followers Twitter – 700 tweets, 400 followers.	YouTube – 300 Videos live w. 3000 hits Facebook – 2500 followers Twitter – 1200 tweets, 1500 followers.
Networking events and workshops	Attend and/or host up to 3 relevant networking events or workshops addressing the target communities, stakeholders and end-users.	Attend and/or host up to 5 relevant networking events or workshops addressing the target communities, stakeholders and users.	Attend and/or host up to 5 relevant networking events or workshops addressing the target communities, stakeholders and users.
Positive media coverage & releasing publications	1 newsletter; 2-4 project publications (articles, papers presentation); At least 9 blog entries.	2-3 newsletters 4-6 project publications. At least 20 blog entries.	3-4 newsletters 5-10 project publications more than 70 blog entries.
Cluster with Relevant projects & initiatives	Cluster with DS projects such as: Ghost, SerIoT.	Cluster with 2 relevant projects or global initiatives.	Cluster with 5 relevant projects or global initiatives.

Table 7: Dissemination and Communication KPI's

The following table (Table 8) lists the project KPIs, regarding what was planned and what was implemented during the first eighteen months. The main goal is to complete, all pending activities so that the KPI values reach the desired result.

Communication and Dissemination Channels	Year 1	Year2	Results (M1-M18)
Create Project Identity & Branding	Create project branding and identity. Final Logo and colour scheme.	Revise Branding and Identity as required by project partners.	Achieved
Design Dissemination Materials	Publicity materials: leaflet/ brochure, poster & other.	Update materials according to progress.	Leaflet created
Create Project Website	Launch website (project overview, communication platform).	Update the website with portal information and open data repository.	Deliverable 8.3 / www.niove.eu
Implement effective social media strategy	YouTube – Video live w. 1000 hits Facebook – 400 followers Twitter – 150 followers.	YouTube – 3 Videos live w. 2000 hits Facebook – 800 followers Twitter – 400 followers.	Video – under preparation Facebook – 99 followers Twitter – 46 followers LinkedIn – 100 followers
Networking events and workshops	Attend and/or host up to 3 relevant networking events or workshops addressing the target communities, stakeholders and end-users.	Attend and/or host up to 5 relevant networking events or workshops addressing the target communities, stakeholders, and users.	13 events achieved (see subsections 8.2.3 and 9.1.4)
Positive media coverage & releasing publications	1 newsletter; 2-4 project publications (articles, papers presentation); At least 9 blog entries.	2-3 newsletters 4-6 project publications At least 20 blog entries.	Newsletter postponed for Year 2; 5 Publications achieved (see subsections 8.2.4 and 9.1.5)
Cluster with Relevant projects & initiatives	Cluster with DS projects such as: Ghost, SerIoT.	Cluster with 2 relevant projects or global initiatives.	ICTLC organized a webinar together with and the PREVENT project which

			supports the Commission actions that aim to promote the development, deployment and use of Intelligent Integrated Safety Systems in Europe, talking about our participation in nloVe and generally cybersecurity aspects of CAVs.
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Table 8: Identification of KPIs for each Communication Tool - Year1

The consortium will strive towards more reports, blog posts and social networks posts by being more active and engaged. A press release and newsletter were about to be published but it was decided that it would be more effective to publish them after finalizing the initial project results.

11 Conclusions and future work

The present plan provides the guidelines to be followed for the communication (i.e. brochures, internal reports & presentations, video, etc.) of nloVe's objectives and results as well as the overall strategy for its dissemination (i.e. plan of participation to conferences, workshops, demos, etc.). The main tools of dissemination and communication of the project were presented in detail. Relevant audiences and stakeholders to target are identified along with the appropriate channels to use.

The main goal of this deliverable is to present the dissemination strategy and its results during the first eighteen months of project implementation along with the planned activities of the second year. The dissemination methods and their results have been classified into categories, so that the way we reach the key audience is constantly improving. Some of the methods we used are the presence on social media, updating the website and participating in events related to the areas of action of the project. The use of social media has not yet led to the desired penetration, but the fact that social media appearances are enhanced shows us that the results will improve during the second year.

It is worth mentioning that the spread of the coronavirus has led to the cancellation of events and meetings which had a considerable effect on the dissemination activities of the project. Nevertheless, communication efforts were made to overcome this barrier by updating the website and improving nloVe's social media presence.

The dissemination strategy will be checked and redefined at regular intervals to ensure the proper promotion and exploitation of the project. Finally, the current plan will be updated, regularly in order to examine the results of the methods of dissemination and communication strategy of the project and to renew the original methods with the primary goal of achieving the desired results.